

Open Feedback Form

[omitted for review]

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Instructions

This form gathers open-ended feedback to refine and improve the platform, complementing the structured questionnaire results.

Section: Improvement Suggestions

1. What were the main strengths of the platform?

2. What limitations or usability issues did you encounter?

3. What specific improvements would you suggest for future versions?

4. Any additional comments or reflections you would like to share?
